

NADH Driven Enzymatic Carboxylic Acid Reduction

Jonathan Guyang Ling,^[a] Hannah G. Breuer,^[b] Holly Stolterfoht-Stock,^[c]
Farah Diba Abu Bakar,^[a] and Margit Winkler*^[b, c]

Dedicated to the memory of Prof. Helmut Schwab

Carboxylic acid reductases (CARs) are versatile biocatalysts for aldehyde production from carboxylic acids. The redox cofactor utilized by CARs is NADPH and no explicitly NADH-dependent CARs have been described so far. Especially in view of cell free applications which necessitate cofactor recycling, NADH-dependent enzymes are more appealing due to higher cofactor stability, lower cost, and more flexibility in the choice of recycling systems. We aimed to extend the current toolbox of CARs with NADH-dependent enzymes and explored a yet untapped

family of putative CARs. A CAR derived from *Clostridium bourniense* was readily produced in *Escherichia coli* and its cofactor preference studied in detail and compared to that of known CARs. Most surprisingly, many of the work-horse enzymes like *Mycobacterium marinum* CAR are able to utilize NADH as a cofactor. In conclusion, NADPH remains the preferred cofactor for all CARs studied herein, but conversions can reach almost the same levels with both cofactors in some cases.

1. Introduction

Enzymatic reduction of carboxylic acids by carboxylic acid reductases (CARs) is driven by ATP to activate the acid, and NADPH as a hydride donor for reduction of an intermediate enzyme bound thioester (Scheme 1A).^[1,2] In detail, CARs comprise of three domains, for three consecutive reactions, respectively. The first is the activation of a carboxylate in the adenylation domain (A-domain). Second, a transthioylation of the acyl by a phosphopantetheine moiety takes place in the thioylation domain (T-domain, ACP or PCP-domain), and finally, the enzyme-bound thioester intermediate is reduced to an aldehyde in the reductase domain (R-domain).^[3] This enzymatic reaction cascade has been explored for the synthesis of a large variety of aldehydes and alcohols,^[4-6] as well as other follow up products of aldehydes^[7] by coupling the system to subsequent chemical^[8,9] or enzymatic transformations.^[6,10-13]

Five distinct clans of CARs have been described to date: Type I consists of CARs of mostly bacterial lineage, while Types II to IV consist of CARs discovered from a broad spectrum of fungi. The fifth Type of CARs are represented by enzymes of similar A-T-R domain architecture with a specialized preference for amino acid substrates.^[4] While sequence similarity between different CAR Types is generally low,^[12] the Type I CARs are relatively more conserved and show less divergence in sequence, function and structure. However, it must also be noted that almost all type I CARs reported to date originate from Actinomycetota,^[14] and this somewhat skews our view of the true diversity within the type I clan of CARs.

Acid reduction by CARs is commonly described to be driven by ATP and NADPH, respectively.^[15] The somewhat dogmatic NADPH dependence of thioester reduction in the R-domains of CARs seemed puzzling, because NADH-dependent thioester reductase (TR) domains have been described in the context of polyketide synthesis.^[16] In the biosynthesis of zeamine in *Serratia plymuthica*, a multi-modular assembly line consisting of five polypeptides that constitute a Type I iterative polyketide synthase termed Zmn10-14 includes a standalone thioester reductase (Zmn14) that off-loads the aldehyde precursor of the pentaaminoalcohol zeamine II in an NADH-dependent fashion. The module was produced in *E. coli* and it showed activity for the reduction of dodecanoyl-CoA, octanoyl-CoA, and butyryl-CoA with a strong preference of NADH vs NADPH as the reducing equivalent.^[17] Similarly, the terminal domain of module 5 (CpkC) of the polyketide synthase Cpk from *Streptomyces coelicolor* is a thioester reductase domain that releases 5-hydroxydodeca-2,6,8,10-tetraeneal as an intermediate in the biosynthetic pathway of coelimycin. The strict NADH preference of the standalone thioester reductase was confirmed in vitro.^[18]

In the context of biocatalysis, cofactor selectivity for NADH is preferable due to its cheaper cost and its higher stability when compared to NADPH. Cofactor switch of NADPH-dependent oxi-

[a] J. G. Ling, Prof. F. D. A. Bakar
Department of Biological Sciences and Biotechnology, Universiti
Kebangsaan Malaysia, Bangi, Selangor 43600, Malaysia

[b] H. G. Breuer, Dr. M. Winkler
Institute of Molecular Biotechnology, Graz University of Technology,
Petersgasse 14, Graz 8010, Austria
E-mail: margitwinkler@acib.at
margit.winkler@tugraz.at

[c] H. Stolterfoht-Stock, Dr. M. Winkler
Austrian Centre of Industrial Biotechnology, Krenngasse 37, Graz 8010,
Austria

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Scheme 1. A) Reaction cascade from acid to aldehyde catalyzed by CARs; (B) This work: NADH dependent acid reduction.

doreductases has been subject to previous studies.^[19] We were also encouraged by previous reports of reductase domains with preferential NADH dependence and the modular nature of the constituent CAR domains, and aimed to explore the carboxylic acid reductase sequence space for candidates with putative NADH-dependent reductase domains.

2. Results and Discussion

Switching the cofactor specificity has not yet been attempted in CAR enzymes. The general consensus is that specificity for NAD(H) or NADP(H) is determined by the charge and polarity of the cofactor binding pocket: NADPH-preferring enzymes possess larger binding pockets lined with positively charged or hydrogen bond donating amino acid residues that form interactions with the phosphate group of the adenosine ribose,^[20] while in NADH-preferring enzymes the binding pocket contains negatively charged amino acids that repulse the negatively-charged phosphate group of NADPH and form hydrogen bonds with the 2'-OH and 3'-OH groups of the adenosine ribose.^[21] There is also the possibility that other discrete recognition elements are involved. However, to date none of these elements have been shown to be universal in the characteristics it imparts nor are they generally deterministic in nature. Based on structural superimposition with the *Mm*CAR R-domain (PDB: 5MSO), three amino acids, that is T693, R718, and R725 in the $\beta 2\alpha 3$ loop in the cofactor binding Rossmann-fold of the R-domain of *Nc*CAR (PDB: 8AEP) were identified to be involved in the binding of the phosphate group of the adenosine ribose. Previous studies have shown that the first conserved arginine (R718 in *Nc*CAR) stabilizes the binding of the cofactor through π -stacking and cation- π interactions with the adenine ring system of the cofactor. Although not indispensable, the absence of this residue leads to a remarkable decrease in activity due to a weaker binding of adenine cofactors in general.^[22] The role of these arginine residues in additional interactions with the cofactor thus disqualified them from mutational studies.

We selected the conserved threonine residue (T693) located on the glycine-rich motif region on the loop upstream of $\alpha 2$ for initial mutational studies. Repulsion of NADPH in the T693D and T693E variants were more pronounced as shown by the almost complete abolishment of NADPH-dependent activity (Figure S3). Both enzyme variants showed increased NADH-dependent activ-

ity, that is 172- and 267-fold for the T693 and T693E variants respectively, but this is still more than one order of magnitude lower than the original activity with NADPH, which is in line with literature.^[21,22]

Complementing the cofactor-switching strategy, we opted for a discovery approach. The amino acid sequence of the *Streptomyces coelicolor* type I PKS, CpkC (GenBank Accession WP_046496888.1)^[18] was used as a query for a BLASTp^[23] search of the non-redundant protein sequences (nr) database with 5000 as the parameter in Max target sequences. CpkC was the query because its R domain is NADH-dependent, unlike R-domains of known CARs. Not surprisingly, the hitlist contained predominantly large PKS modules. We next discarded sequences shorter than 980 or longer than 1400 amino acids (AAs), because 980–1400 AAs is a sensible size range for proteins composed of A-T-R domain architecture. The hits were manually investigated based on the conserved domain prediction in the Traditional Results Page view of the BLASTp suite. The first hit with A-T-R domain architecture was used as a query for a second BLASTp search of the nr database. The resulting hitlist was inspected for proteins with essential CAR residues H237, S595, Y844, and K848 (numbering refers to *Neurospora crassa* CAR^[24]), and *Eubacterium ramulus* thioester reductase domain-containing protein (GenBank Accession WP_154314264.1) was the first identified hit with the desired domain architecture and essential CAR residues in place. Approximately 30 more homologues were analyzed in detail and ranked, amongst other parameters for predicted solubility using the SoDoPE tool.^[25] The most promising sequence appeared to be a thioester reductase domain-containing protein from *Clostridium bornimense* (GenBank Protein Accession WP_216461348.1), which we named *Cb1*CAR. The Type I CARs are the most well explored and studied group among the carboxylic acid reductase enzyme family; and all of the sequences reported to date originate from the domain Bacteria while half of the reported CARs of the Type V clan are of bacterial lineage. In order to understand the position of *Cb1*CAR in the sequence space of the carboxylic acid reductase enzyme family, we performed phylogenetic and sequence similarity network analyses. *Cb1*CAR is phylogenetically distinct from all previously reported CARs and does not fall into any of the previously defined Types (Figure 1).

Unexpectedly, our phylogenetic analysis also showed that the recently reported CARs from *Novosphingobium malaysiense* (a Gram-negative bacterium from the phylum Pseudomonadota)^[5] belong to the Type I clan of CARs, while the CARs from *Coccomyxa subellipsoidea* (a unicellular, eukaryotic green algae from the phylum/division Chlorophyta), *Cs*CAR,^[5] and *Cafeteria roenbergensis* (a marine flagellate from the phylum Bigyra), *Cr*CAR^[26] we classified as ungrouped due to their ambiguous phylogenetic grouping.

A sequence similarity network (SSN) for the bacterial members of the carboxylic acid reductase enzyme family was then generated using a library of 3305 unique bacterial CAR sequences mined from the InterPro databases. The SSN was displayed at various e-value thresholds (Figure 2). At an e-value threshold of 10^{-103} (where $\sim 30\%$ sequence identity is required to visualize edges between nodes), the majority of CARs are grouped into a single cluster that is functionally heterogeneous

Figure 1. Phylogenetic analysis of the carboxylic acid reductase enzyme family.

Figure 2. Sequence similarity networks (SSNs) of carboxylic acid reductases of bacterial lineage. (A) The SSN displayed at an e-value threshold of 10^{-103} (~30% sequence identity). (B) The SSN displayed at an e-value threshold of 10^{-208} (~40% sequence identity); Experimentally confirmed sequences are highlighted and partly labelled. Nodes colored according to the CAR classification: Type I in blue, Type V in green (HamD cluster), yellow (*BtCAR* cluster), purple (GupB cluster), salmon (ATRed cluster), the new *CbCAR* cluster in cyan.

Figure 3. Effect of pH on *Cb1CAR*. Substrate: 2 mM octanoic acid; 2 mM NADH, 2 mM ATP. MES buffer (100 mM) with 6 mM MgCl₂, 200 mM NaCl, 1 mM DTT. Reaction time: 4 h. Analysis: GC/FID. Black: carboxylic acid **a**, green: aldehyde **b**, teal blue: alcohol **c**.

(Figure 2A). When the network is displayed at a higher e-value threshold stringency of 10^{-208} (where $\sim 40\%$ sequence identity is required to visualize an edge), the sequences separate into 33 clusters (with 3 or more members) and the remaining as duos or singletons (Figure 2B). Here, we see that the largest cluster of nodes belong to the Type I clan (cluster in blue), while the remaining Type V CARs with experimentally characterized functions are spread throughout 4 separate clusters (clusters in green, yellow, purple and salmon). The *Cb1CAR* grouped into a cluster that is distinct from all previously reported CARs (cluster in cyan). These results underline that *Cb1CAR* is distinct from all previously reported CARs (supporting information Table S2) and has exposed the unexplored extent of the carboxylic acid reductase family sequence space, showing that the CAR enzyme family is much more functionally diverse and evolutionally divergent than currently recognized.

Overexpression of a codon optimized gene coding for WP_216461348.1 in *E. coli* K-12 MG1655 RARE^[27] produced soluble protein with the expected molecular mass according to SDS PAGE analysis. The protein *Cb1CAR* was produced and purified following the well-established protocols for CARs. Its tendency to aggregate was circumvented by the addition of 0.2 M NaCl and 0.005% Tween 20. The first evidence of activity was obtained for purified protein in a spectrophotometric activity assay monitoring the depletion of NADH in the presence of octanoic acid (**1a**). The pH preference of *Cb1CAR* was explored (pH 5.0–pH 8.5) using the purified protein for end-point biotransformation reactions followed by GC-based product quantification. The buffer was supplemented with DTT to protect the phosphopantetheine thiol against oxidation. *Cb1CAR* appears to be most active below pH 6.0. Since protein precipitation was observed at pH 5.5 or lower, we concluded that pH 5.8 facilitated the highest operational stability (Figure 3).

In order to gain insight into the substrate scope of *Cb1CAR*, short chain carboxylic acids were investigated as substrates using the spectrophotometric cofactor depletion assay (Supporting Information Figure S2). The enzyme showed activity for acids of chain length from C-6 to C-8, but no significant consumption of reducing equivalents occurred when acetic acid, pentanoic acid, long chain fatty acids, piperonylic acid, 3,4-dihydroxyphenyl acetic acid, pyrazine-carboxylic acid, 4-nitrobenzoic acid or tyrosine, was present. Medium chain carboxylic acids were tested

as *Cb1CAR* substrates in whole cell biotransformations (Supporting Information Figures S4 and S5, respectively). In summary, *Cb1CAR* showed activity for linear carboxylates with chain-lengths between C-6 and C-10, with a preference for C-8 and C-9. The specific activity of *Cb1CAR*, however, was significantly lower than that of well known *MmCAR* for the same substrates.

The major selection criterion for the choice of *Cb1CAR* had been the similarity of its R-domain with NADH-dependent thioester reductase domains. Hence, the assumption that NADPH would not be used as a cofactor was challenged. IMAC enriched *Cb1CAR* was incubated in the presence of **1a** and ATP under identical conditions with either NADH or NADPH and the samples were analyzed by GC. Notably, there was significant conversion with both cofactors: With NADH, 14% of octanal (**1b**) and 14% of octanol (**1c**) were detected, while the presence of NADPH led to 4% **1b** and 26% **1c**, respectively. To our surprise, the control reactions with a classical bacterial CAR (*Mycobacterium wolinskyi* *MwCAR*)^[28] gave 45% of **1b** in the presence of NADH, although the current understanding is that CARs are dependent on NADPH.^[1,15,29–31] For comparison, 56% **1b** and traces of **1c** were produced by *MwCAR* in the presence of NADPH under identical conditions (MES buffer, pH6.5). Notably, initial rate NAD(P)H consumption assays had shown CAR activity only in the presence of NADPH for *NcCAR*^[1] and several other CARs including *MmCAR* in our lab (unpublished) indicating that activity is easily overlooked when limiting screening experiments to initial rate measurements.

The above results prompted us to revisit the cofactor preference of CARs more systematically. Table 1 summarizes the results for representative CARs (Supporting Information Table S1), all produced by *E. coli* RARE and IMAC purified. For bacterial CARs, a preference of NADPH can be deduced, however, substitution by NADH leads to almost comparable product titers. In the case of Type III CARs (*NcCAR* and *TtCAR*) the cofactor choice influenced the product distribution: particularly *NcCAR* reduced **1a** to **1c** in the presence of NADH but less in the presence of NADPH.

Type IV CARs showed the most pronounced preference for NADPH, since in the presence of NADH less than half of the product titers were observed. In every case, NADPH is indeed the preferred cofactor. However, NADH is clearly able to fuel thioester reduction.

We then challenged NADH-driven reductions with *MmCAR* including ADH mediated cofactor recycling. As expected using ADH-A with 2-propanol or 2-heptanol as the sacrificial substrate, carboxylic acid is reduced. Notably, piperonylic acid reduction resulted in the respective alcohol rather than piperonal due to aldehyde reducing activity of ADH-A (Supporting Information Figure S6).

The cofactor preference of *Cb1CAR* appeared to be very similar to that of bacterial CARs with only a slight advantage of NADPH over NADH. Remarkably, the major product of *Cb1CAR* was the alcohol **1c** (Table 1, two bottom entries). Contributions of protein impurities to **1b** reduction were minimized by purification of *Cb1CAR* by size exclusion chromatography (Supporting Information Figure S1) and the major product was still **1c** with both cofactors. The low activity in combination with alcohol formation suggests that *Cb1CAR* may have a different natural

Table 1. Cofactor dependence of IMAC purified CARs. Black: carboxylic acid **a**, green: aldehyde **b**, teal blue: alcohol **c**; Conditions as in Figure 2, pH 6.5. NaCl only present in reactions with *Cb1CAR*.

Enzyme(Type)	Enzyme Conc. [μg]	Substrate	NADH	NADPH
<i>MwCAR</i> (I)	120	1a		
<i>MmCAR</i> (I)	116	1a		
<i>NiCAR</i> (I)	142	1a		
<i>NcCAR</i> (III)	81	1a		
<i>TtCAR</i> (III)	145	1a		
<i>Pc2CAR</i> (IV)	145	1a		
<i>Pc2CAR</i> (IV)	145	2a		
<i>Pc4CAR</i> (IV)	384	1a		
<i>Pc4CAR</i> (IV)	99	2a		
<i>Cb1CAR</i> (ungrouped)	310	1a		
<i>Cb1CAR</i> ^{a)} (ungrouped)	191	1a		

^{a)} purified by size exclusion chromatography.

function that remains to be elucidated. These results demonstrate that this enzyme, and perhaps its whole cluster, may not hold enough potential to warrant further pursue at least not in the context of biocatalytic synthesis of aldehydes.

3. Conclusion

In conclusion, carboxylic acid reductases can be fuelled not only with NADPH but also with NADH, which is particularly valuable for cell free applications of CARs and greatly extends the opera-

tional freedom in terms of the choice of recycling systems. A new CAR (*Cb1CAR*) from a yet unexplored cluster of A-T-R domain proteins was characterized. This protein is efficiently produced in *E. coli* and demonstrated a strong tendency to 4-electron reduction to give the alcohols from the respective carboxylic acids in the presence of either NADH or NADPH as the reducing equivalent. Phylogenetic analysis of experimentally confirmed CARs revealed increasing diversity and still a number of unexplored clades in the bacterial space.

Supporting Information

Additional tables, figures and experimental details (DOC). The authors have cited additional references within the Supporting Information.^[32–43]

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available in the supplementary material of this article.

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